

AWARENESS AMONG TRIBAL PARENTS ABOUT EDUCATIONAL FACILITIES OF THEIR STUDENTS WITH SPECIAL NEEDS

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Abstract

The study attempt to compare the awareness about educational opportunites of children with special needs of tribal parents with regard to their level of education and social setting. The sample for the study is total 150 tribal parents selected randomly for the study. An interview schedule for the parents is used to collect the information about the awreness of educational facilities of studnets with speical needs. The major findings of the study are literate tribal parents were more aware about educational opportunites of their children with special needs than illiterate parents. Furhter, educated parents were more aware about the educational opportunites of chidlren with special needs than illiterate parents.

Keyword: awareness, educational facilities, studnets with special needs

Introduction

Ours is a democratic set up, which relies on equal rights equal opportunities. So, to ensure that the disabled are accepted, respected and not discriminated upon in schools a follow up becomes necessary. Global figures estimate that approximately 15 percent of the population is disabled. So the educational opportunites of these disabled should be provided to them for their better development. Parents involvement, attitude and level of awareness is important for fulfilling the educational demand of children with special needs. So far the tribal parents are concerned, they are less educated, literacy rate among tribal people is very less as compare to non-tribal people, so these tribal community is not so aware about the educational opportunites of their disabled kids. Hence, the present study is undertaken to find out the awareness level of tribal and non-tribal parents about the educational opportunites of their children with special needs.

From the review of related literature and research studies it is revealed that very few studies have been underatken so far in the area of special education especuilly on the parents of disabled children on india and abroad. Studoes conducted by Blackard and Barsh (1982) on 'parents and professional peception of the handicapped child' impact on the family', Seligman and Meyrson(1982) undertook a study on 'Group approaches for parents of exceptional children and Penthol (2005) studied the developmental framework of guidance and counselling for the parents of the children with special needs and found that parental awarness is importnat for the education of their kids.

Odisha being poverty stricken state with a sizeable number of tribal populaiton needs speical attention of government and non-government sectors for the provision of education and needs bases education for the employment of the children in general and children with special needs in particular for the economic and social development of the state. So the present study is undertake to findout the awareness level of parents having students with special needs about their educational facilities.

Methods

Tools: The investigator developed intrview schedule for the teachers. After the formulation of the questions, the investigator set the structure of questions in very simple and objective manners which were open and

close ended. The content of the information schedule for teachers was constructed and to seek information from the teachers of special and integrated schools. The investigator at the initial stage prepared a set of 20 questions. After consulting the subject experts, administrators and headmasters the content validity was found and 10 questions were retained in final draft and 10 items were dropped from the interview schedule for the teachers of the schools.

Table-1

Significance of difference between illiterate and literate tribal parents on awareness about educational opportunities of their children with special needs

Group of parents	N	Mean	SD	SED	t-ratio	Level of significance
Illiterate	50	77.67	3.45	0.71	5.55	.01**
Literate	50	81.61	3.67			

The Table-1 revealed that the mean scores of illiterate and literate tribal parents on awareness about the educational opportunities of their children with special needs are 77.67 and 81.61 with SDs 3.45 and 3.67 respectively. The t-ratio came out from the above two groups is 5.55 which is significant at .01 level of significance. That means there is significant difference between above two groups on awareness about educational opportunities of children with special needs. Moreover, the mean scores of literate tribal parents is higher than illiterate parents. It indicates that literate parents were more aware about the educational opportunities of their children with special needs than illiterate parents. Thus the hypothesis (H-1) that the 'literate tribal parents were more aware about educational opportunities of their children with special needs than illiterate parents' is accepted.

Mean scores of illiterate and literate tribal parents on educational opportunities for their children with special needs as depicted in table-1 is represented by the bar Fig. 1

Table-2
Significance of difference between illiterate and educated tribal parents on awareness educational opportunities of their children with special needs

Group of parents	N	Mean	SD	SED	t-ratio	Level of significance
Illiterate	50	77.67	3.45	0.74	6.46	.01
Educated	50	82.45	4.01			

The Table 4.27 revealed that the mean scores of illiterate and educated tribal parents on awareness about the educational opportunities of their children with special needs are 77.67 and 82.45 with SDs 3.45 and 4.01 respectively. The t-ratio came out from the above two groups is 6.46 which is significant at .01 level of significance. That means there is significant difference between above two groups on awareness about educational opportunities of their children with special needs. However, the mean scores of educated tribal parents is higher than illiterate parents. It indicates that educated parents were more aware about the educational opportunities of children with special needs than illiterate parents.

Thus the hypothesis (H-2) that the ‘educated tribal parents were more aware about educational opportunities of their children with special needs than illiterate parents’ is accepted.

Mean scores of illiterate and literate tribal parents on educational opportunities for their children with special needs as depicted in table 4.27 is represented by the bar Fig. 2

Table-4.28

Significance of difference between literate and educated tribal parents on awareness about educational opportunities of thier children with special needs

Group of parents	N	Mean	SD	SED	t-ratio	Level of significance
Literate	50	81.61	3.67	0.76	1.11	Not sig.
Educated	50	82.45	4.01			

The Table 4.28 revealed that the mean scores of literate and educated tribal parents on awarness about educational oportunites of their children with special needs are 81.61 and 82.45 with SDs 3.67 and 4.01 respectively. The t-ratio came out from the above two groups is 1.11 which is not significant at both level of significance. That means there is no significant difference between above two groups on awareness about educational oportunites of children with special needs. However, the mean scores of educated tribal parents is higher than listrate parents. It indicates that educated parents were more aware about the educational oportunites of their children with special needs than listrate parents.

Thus the hypothesis (H-3) that the ‘educated tribal parents were more aware about educational oportunites of their children with special needs than literate parents’ is rejected.

Mean scores of listrate and educated tribal parents on educational oportunites for their children with special needs as depicted in table 4.28 is represented by the bar Fig. 3

Findings and Discussion

There is a significant difference among tribal parents about awareness about educational facilities of thier students with special needs. So far educated parents are concerned they were more aware about the educational facilities than literate parents. Further, literate parents were more aware than the illiterate parents about the awareness of educational facilities of their children. Educational level of parents plays a significant role to get awareness about educational facilities of disables. So it is suggested that authority, administrator, stakeholsres should create awareness about different facilities of disabled among illiterate

parents through mass media, poster and drama (nukkad). There should be arranged parents meeting. Participate workshop, seminar about disability to make them aware.

Reference

- Annalaug, F., Torill, M. & Sigua, G. (2004). Towards inclusive schools: A study of inclusive education in practice. *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 19 (1), 85-98
- Begum, S. (2003). *Cognitive development in blind children*, New Delhi: Discovering Publishing House.
- David, L.D. and Lise, F. (2007). *Teaching students with severe disabilities*. Bristol: Center for Studies in Inclusive Education.
- Hegarty, S., Pocklington, K. & Lucas, D. (1982). *Integration in Action*. Slough: NFER-Nelson.
- Jenkinson, J.C. (1993). Integration of students with service and multiple learning difficulties, *European Journal of Special Needs Education*, 9(1),27-39.
- Julka, A. (2005). Cognitive architecture in the visually impaired. *Disabilities and Impairment*,19(1),5-14.
- Kamboj, R. (2010). *Social skills among visually impaired students studying in inclusive and special schools*. M.Ed. Dissertation, Kurukshetra: Kurukshetra University.
- Kumar, D. (2011). *Social skills of visually impaired students in relation to their academic achievement*. M.Ed. Dissertation, Kurukshetra: Kurukshetra University
- Majda, S. & Branka, C. (2006) Classroom climate in regular primary school settings with children with special needs. *Educational Research*, 32 (4), 361 -372.
- Malik, S. (2009). *Personality development of students with special needs studying in integrated and special schools*. M.Phil. Dissertation, Sirsa: Ch. Devi Lal University.
- Meadow, K.P (1980). *Deafness and child development*, Great Britain: The Regents of the University of California.
- Mrug, S. & Wallander, J.L. (2002). Self-concept of young people with physical disabilities; does integration play a role? *International Journal of Disabilities, Development and Education*, 49(3), 267-280.
- Pradhan, S.K. (2010). Personality characteristics of visually impaired students in inclusive and special schools. *Ambikeya: Journal of Education*, 1(2), 25-29.
- Rai, N.K. (1992). Comprehension of visually handicapped children using audio and tactile: a comprehension, *Indian Journal of Disability and Rehabilitation*, 3(1),12-19.
- Ruijs, N.M. and Peetsma, T.T.D. (2009). Effects of inclusion on students with and without special educational needs reviewed, *Educational Research Review*, 34 (4), 67–79.
- Sahu, B.K. (2005). *Education of the exceptional children*, Ludhiana: Kalyani Publishers
- Sharma, A. (2009). *Personality development of orthopedically impaired students studying in integrated and special schools*. M.Ed. dissertation, Kurukshetra: Kurukshetra University
- Sharma, S.K.(2004). *Comparative study of self-concept and self-esteem of blinds students studying in integrated and special school setting*. New Delhi: Ph.D. Thesis, I. A. S. E, faculty of education, Jamia Millia Islamia University,
- Sharma, V. (2001). *Cognitive style and language comprehension of the blind*. New Delhi: Rajat Publication.
- Singh, R., Shyam, R. & Kumar, S. (2006). *Socio-economic status scale*, Agra: National Psychological corporation.
- Trevor, R.P., Stewart L. E., Bruce J.T. & John, A.D. (1998). Behavioral and emotional problems in the classroom children and adolescent with intellectual disability. *Journal Of Intellectual and Developmental Disability*, 23(1), 71-77.